

Perspective Projection Approach to a Faster UAV Navigation and Obstacle Avoidance Learning

Stefani Kecman
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Sarajevo
Sarajevo, Bosnia&Herzegovina
skecman1@etf.unsa.ba

Dinko Osmankovic
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Sarajevo
Sarajevo, Bosnia&Herzegovina
dinko.osmankovic@etf.unsa.ba

Abstract—Interest in research of the navigation problem for Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is on the rise. The aim of such a task is reaching a goal position while avoiding obstacles on the way. In this paper, we propose a different approach to Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) of navigation decision making process by introducing the reward function based of Artificial Potential Fields (APF). The validation of the proposed approach is performed by the comparison to the state-of-the-art approach. In terms of training performance, success rate, memory usage and the inference time, our approach, though sparser in terms of perceived information about the environment, yield better results.

Index Terms—perspective projection, deep reinforcement learning, artificial potential fields, navigation function, deep Q-learning, UAV

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have become increasingly popular platforms for research and engineering. Furthermore, autonomy of the UAVs has been the main focus of research with navigation being one of the many problems within this field. Considering this, UAVs can be viewed as autonomous agents and with the developments in the field of deep reinforcement learning authors have started exploring solutions in this context [1]–[3].

The main part of this paradigm is the action-state principle illustrated in Fig. 1. An agent (UAV in this case) navigates through an environment by employing predefined set of actions. Meanwhile, the environments acknowledges that the agent is interacting with it and rewards the agent in some way. In order to establish these interactions, UAVs are usually equipped with several types of sensors: odometry, GPS, lidars, RGB and depth cameras, *etc.* Some research deals with usage of a single type of sensor [1], [2], while others use multi-sensor approach [4]. Using cameras and computer vision is an important approach to implementing interactions with the environment which lead to the solutions to the important problems in autonomous systems such as obstacle avoidance [5]–[7] and path planning [8].

When considering navigation and obstacle avoidance, it must be noted that many of these problems are solved using classical techniques [9]–[11]. However, in this paper, we focus on deep reinforcement learning approach to solving this particular problem.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the Action-State Principle in Reinforcement Learning

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. The next section discusses related work in the fields of navigation, obstacle avoidance and deep reinforcement learning describing different approaches to these problems. Section III details the proposed approach to a faster learning of navigation and obstacle avoidance, followed by a simulation study in section IV. Finally, the paper ends with the conclusion and the discussion about the future work.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND RELATED WORK

A. The Navigation Problem

Robot navigation is one of the essential problems in robotics. Formally, we say that the navigation is a procedure of moving a robot (in our case UAV) through its environment from a starting point q_S to a goal point q_G without interacting with obstacles in C_{obs} , which is a set of possible robot positions where such interaction occurs; or the robot has to move through C_{free} from q_S to q_G , which is a set of permissible robot positions, *i.e.* where no interactions with obstacles occur.

Usually, there are two types of robot navigation: global and local. Global navigation deals with fully observable environment, while local navigation deals with partially or locally observable environment [12]. In this paper we will focus on the problem of global navigation and specifically artificial potential fields (APF). This is a nature-inspired method that defines two types of potential functions: attractive potential for

a goal and a repulsive potential for obstacles [12]. This potential function yields conservative forces that, when summed as vectors, will guide a robot to a goal position while avoiding obstacles.

Formally, we define the APF scalar function as follows:

$$U(q) = U_{att}(q) + U_{rep}(q), \quad (1)$$

where $U_{att}(q)$ is the attractive potential and $U_{rep}(q)$ is the repulsive potential in the position q . There are many ways to define these potential functions, but the most common way is introduced in [9]:

$$U_{att} = \frac{1}{2}\xi\|q - q_G\|^2, \quad (2)$$

$$U_{rep}^i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}\eta\left(\frac{1}{\rho} - \frac{1}{\rho_0}\right)^2 & \text{if } \rho \leq \rho_0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \rho > \rho_0, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$U_{rep} = \sum_i U_{rep}^i, \quad (4)$$

where q is the current robot position, ρ_0 is the limit distance of the potential field influence, ρ is the shortest distance to the i -th obstacle, while ξ and η are some positive constants. We chose these to be 10 and 2, respectively in order to emphasize goal reaching, while simultaneously penalising moving to the obstacles.

In general, the navigation problem is formulated as Markov decision process in [13], [14], [15], [2], [16], which takes into account agent's current state s_t , performs an action a_t , that transitions him to a new state s_{t+1} while collecting a reward r_t [2].

This problem could be simply described as a decision making process that moves an agent from a starting point to a goal point, while avoiding collisions. The reward function guides it towards the global minima, which is, if appropriately defined, the goal. The agent can sometimes get stuck in the local minima. However, in [17] the solution to this problem is proposed, deriving conditions under which this situation does not occur for an environment for convex obstacles. On the other hand, in [11] potential gradient descent algorithm (PGDA) was used as a way to solve the local minima problem.

Another optimisation was described in [18] in a form of new repelling potential, resulting in reduction of oscillations and, in addition, smoother trajectory, thanks to the rotational force.

A systematic review of both UAV navigation and RL is provided in [16], describing the main navigation problems and frameworks, as well as RL algorithms and simulation software [16]. Another useful review is [14], analyzing four typical scenarios for UAV navigation application: local obstacle avoidance, indoor navigation, social navigation and multi-robot navigation, as well as the development of navigation using DRL [14].

UAV navigation model is widely applicable in real-life missions, in search & rescue operations after natural disasters, for instance [2]. Several complementary problems were tackled in [19], *e.g.* battery life, combining gathered information

in cases of low or limited visibility, as well as raw image and navigation history of the registered map [19]. Moreover, in [15] an experiment showing that UAV are capable of completing such tasks is carried out, with an approach based on an Approximated Q-learning algorithm that incorporates a PID controller.

B. Deep Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement Learning is a concept where an agent, that makes decisions, explores the environment, while taking actions based on previous experiences and current observation. A reward is received with each employed action, and the agent's goal is to maximize the longstanding cumulative reward [14].

Authors in [20] first introduced the concept of Deep Reinforcement Learning, a model based on convolutional neural network (CNN) trained with Q-learning algorithm to work on and learn in complex environments, Atari 2600 games, to be exact [20]. In [21] a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method for completing navigation tasks in stochastic and dynamic environment is proposed, using Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients (TD3) algorithm. Additionally, [13] used DRL with non-expert helpers (LwH), with sparse reward scheme, proving that LwH with sparse rewards yield better performance, tested on dynamically set learning objectives, compared to state-of-art algorithms at that time [13]. On the other hand, [3] proposed a novel algorithm, a combination of object detection and DRL algorithm, that reduced flying time by 25% and unnecessary turns by 50% [3].

Stable-Baselines3 (SB3) is an open-source library, with many reliable and thoroughly tested deep RL algorithms in Python [22]. It is an extension of Stable-Baselines2 (SB2) [22], implemented in PyTorch [22], [23] and TensorFlow [22], [24]. These algorithms can be used to design the architecture of a DRL agent and compare different DRL approaches.

Most important DRL algorithms are as follows.

a) Q-learning and Double Q-learning: Q-learning presents a strategy of finding an optimal Q-function, by recursively solving Bellman equation [25]:

$$Q^*(s, a) = \mathbb{E}_{s' \approx p(s'|s, a)} \left[r(s') + \gamma \max_{a'} Q^*(s', a') \right]. \quad (5)$$

However, this equation only defines optimal Q-value. To iteratively calculate this value the following formula is proposed:

$$Q_{t+1}(s_t, a_t) = Q_t(s_t, a_t) + \alpha_t(s_t, a_t) \left(r_t + \gamma \max_a Q_t(s_{t+1}, a) - Q_t(s_t, a_t) \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha_t \in [0, 1]$ is learning rate and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is discount factor.

Usually, Q-function is represented in a tabular form, where an action and states are connected with specific reward value. Initially, all values in this table are set to zeros and are iteratively updated with new state transitions, until the functions reaches its optimal value, *i.e.* when no updates occur or after a certain number of iterations [25].

However, both selection and evaluation of actions are represented with the same value, which leads to overestimation of the optimal Q-function [26].

In order to prevent this from happening, Double Q-learning algorithm is proposed, in which selection and evaluation are split up and the two separate value functions are learned [26].

The main problem with a tabular approach is that its size explodes rapidly. To overcome this, deep neural networks for Q-function approximations are proposed.

b) Deep Q Network: Deep Q network (DQN), is a multi-layered neural network that gives a vector of actions with respect to an agent's state. The output of this network estimates the value of Q - function [26].

c) Double Deep Q Network: Double DQN, or DDQN, uses two networks, with a purpose to solve the problem of overestimation that is mentioned earlier. In conclusion, it has an action selection network and a target network [25].

d) Deterministic Policy Gradient and Related Algorithms: Deterministic Policy Gradient (DPG) is a deterministic policy gradient algorithm [27]. It is based on an actor-critic algorithm where the actor is a policy to be learnt, and the critic approximates the Q - function [27].

A Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient is an algorithm based on the DPG algorithm. Also, actor and critic are built on deep neural networks (DNN). In order to increase the agent's stability, a copy of both actor and critic are stored in target network which provide target values [27].

e) Advantage Actor Critic and Related Algorithms: Advantage Actor Critic (A2C) is an actor - critic approach that introduces a concept of advantage [28]. Asynchronous Advantage Actor Critic (A3C) is an asynchronous version of A2C algorithm. It results in estimating the value function and keeping agent's policy [29]. However, A2C shows better performance than A3C in some scenarios because of its synchronous nature.

III. UAV NAVIGATION LEARNING

The main objective of this paper was to create an agent that learns the APF navigation function on its own while exploring the environment using depth imaging camera that provides information about distance to the obstacles.

A. Construction of an Observation Vector

In our research, we construct the observations of the environment as a $N \times 3$ matrix. We take N closest points from the depth image, based on distance. Each row of this matrix consists of three values: the first one being the distance from the obstacle, second is the calculated azimuth (yaw) angle, and the third is the calculated elevation (pitch) angle. Number of points, in this paper, is chosen to be $N = 10$, as it is a compromise between simplicity and the richness of the information about the environment. The azimuth and the pitch angles are illustrated in Fig. 2, based on the perspective projection of a world point P into the point p in the image plane.

Fig. 2. Bearing angles of a point P with a projection onto image plane

Fig. 3. DQN Agent architecture

The following formulae are used for the angles calculations [30]:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y - \frac{w}{2}}{f} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - \frac{h}{2}}{f} \right) \quad (8)$$

where x and y are coordinates (pixels) of an obstacle in the depth image, h and w are the image dimensions and f is the focal length of the camera. The angles θ and ϕ , as defined in previous equations, represent the pitch and the yaw angles of the obstacle P as perceived at the (x, y) coordinate of the depth image.

Now, instead of using the whole depth image as an observation, we use its simplification, but with these two angles we still have enough information about how the obstacles are position around the UAV. This significantly reduces computational complexity of the agent, which will be validated in the next section.

B. DQN Agent Architecture

Originally, the convolutional neural network was employed [31]. However, the construction of a simplified observation vector renders this approach cumbersome, therefore, the proposed agent architecture consists of several fully connected (FC) layers with dropout layers to reduce overfitting. The architecture is given in Fig. 3.

Moreover, we employ the memory enhancement [31] as it provides a mechanism, similar to [20], for sampling from the previous experience and, therefore, faster learning.

To properly assess the learning rate and design more natural movement of the UAV, we increased the action space in such a way that the UAV is positioned in the center of a cube and the possible moves are those toward the vertices of the cube. This renders 26 possible actions in total.

C. Reward Function

In this paper, we used the modified APF, as proposed in [11]:

$$U_{att} = \frac{1}{2}\xi\|q - q_G\|^2, \quad (9)$$

$$U_{rep}^i = \begin{cases} k_i^r \frac{q - q_i^o}{d_i(q)^3} \left(\frac{1}{d_i(q)} - \frac{1}{d_i^o} \right) & \text{if } d(q) < d_i^o \\ 0 & \text{if } d(q) \geq d_i^o, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$U_{rep} = \sum_i U_{rep}^i, \quad (11)$$

where q is the current robot position, q_G is the goal position, $d(q)$ is the Euclidean distance between q and q_G , and d_i^o is i -th obstacle's influence. Furthermore, we additionally reward reaching the goal position and penalise collisions with two different constants (positive for reaching the goal and negative for collisions). APF has a global minimum in the goal position, however, the DQN maximizes the reward, so the APF based reward is, in our case, with negative value.

The main advantage of described APF method is that the obstacles' potential is only affected when the robot is near the goal [11]. Furthermore, it overcomes a major drawback of the original APF approach [9], which is due to local minima that induce the standard APF method to trap in. Assumption of this method, however, is that there are no obstacles near the goal, with which the agent would collide upon arriving at the goal [11], therefore, we have chosen the goal positions for training to satisfy this condition.

To overcome the problem of overexploration, we limit the movement of UAV outside of reasonable boundaries and penalise such states as if they are collisions.

IV. RESULTS

In this section we present the results obtained during the simulation study. In our case, used Microsoft Airsim Blocks scenario for the validation of the proposed approach. Furthermore, the code was run on a Desktop PC with AMD Ryzen 5800G, 16GB of RAM, NVIDIA 3060 RTX GPU with CUDA 11.6 and Pytorch 11.6, all installed on Ubuntu Linux 22.04.1. In order to validate the generalisation of our approach, ten randomly selected goals along the shortest Manhattan distance walk between successive goal points are chosen for testing.

In order to have better training, we have chosen to simultaneously train the agent to reach five different goal points. This is illustrated in Fig. 4. These points are chosen in such a way they are "visible" in depth camera's field-of-view (FOV) at the start position and to satisfy the modified APF conditions.

Fig. 4. Goal points in Airsim Blocks scenario used in training

A. Comparison of Training

Fig. 5 depicts the evolution of the reward value in the final position of the UAV. The plots of the mean value of the reward during training epochs are shown for both the original CNN and our simplified approach. Furthermore, for better reading of this figure, we also include averaged plots.

Averaged plot of training evolution for the original CNN approach is marked with orange, while for the proposed approach is marked with red. Since we are training the agent for several goal positions simultaneously, drops in mean reward occur (in cases when collision occurs or some of the final state rewards are much lower). What is clear is that our approach recovers rewards much faster. Moreover, after some 400 epochs, the difference between reward values becomes significant.

We also observe significant decrease (several orders of magnitude) in GPU memory consumption. This is an expected behaviour as CNNs are known for its high memory usage.

B. Validation

To properly validate the proposed approach, we first performed the tests that show whether the agent learns correctly. We set the same goal position that were used for training and allow the trained agent 200 steps (actions) to reach the goal position. Results are presented in Table. I.

Note that if UAV cannot reach the goal position with 200 steps, we stop the simulation and proceed with another run. For each of the tests, 20 runs are performed and average values are noted.

It is clear that the proposed approach outperforms the CNN based approach. Both success rate (*i.e.* reaching the goal within a radius of $2[m]$) and the average number of moves (actions taken) clearly shows the benefits of the approach. Furthermore, the number of points from the depth image used in the construction of the observation vector seems to be enough, but more experiments are required to properly assess this.

The proposed DQN architecture, with only the FC layers, is simpler compared to the CNN layers. This leads to significant performance boost in inference with some 200-odd [ms] improvement in execution time. This time includes the DQN agent inference, sending the command to Airsim through gRPC, and receiving the acknowledge signal from Airsim.

Fig. 5. Training comparison

TABLE I
VALIDATION OF TRAINING THROUGH REPEATED TESTS

Scenario	CNN Agent			FF Agent (proposed)		
	Success (%)	Average No. Moves	Average Inference Time (ms)	Success (%)	Average No. Moves	Average Inference Time (ms)
Goal 1 Test	40	137	963.11	90	79.8	765.89
Goal 2 Test	35	139.05		85	96.35	
Goal 3 Test	50	123.3		95	58.8	
Goal 4 Test	35	138.6		85	75.1	
Goal 5 Test	30	150.75		75	103.3	
Generalisation Test	20	-		60	-	

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a perspective projection approach to constructing the observation vector to improve learning of navigation and obstacle avoidance for UAVs. The results clearly show the benefits of such an approach, both in terms of training and testing. Simplified agent architecture yield faster learning, better success rates and better generalisation, while consuming significantly less GPU memory. Furthermore, neural network based on fully connected layers reduce the inference time of action selection.

Several problems are detected and will be addressed in the future. Firstly, the number of points representing the simplified depth image needs to be optimally chosen and for this we need further research. Secondly, investigating the behaviour of other DRL algorithms in this context is interesting as well. We plan on reviewing algorithm form SB3 for this purpose. And thirdly, more investigation is required to properly assess the influence of hyper-parameters of the algorithms.

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The code is hosted on <https://github.com/stefanikecman/AeroStream-ICAT-diplomski.git>.

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